
A DESCRIPTIVE STUDY TO ASSESS THE KNOWLEDGE REGARDING MEDICO-LEGAL ASPECTS IN CARE OF PATIENTS AMONG STUDENT NURSES STUDYING IN AMAR PROFESSIONAL COLLEGE OF NURSING, DYALPURA, DISTRICT MOHALI, PUNJAB.

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ABSTRACT

Background: Medico- Legal Aspect refers to medico-legal consideration, definition and ethics that provide the framework for informed consent malpractice, assault, battery and documentation, patient's right and many other aspects like LAMA.

Aim: The objective of this study was to assess knowledge of student's nurses regarding medico legal aspects in care of patients.

Methodology The tool for the study was questionnaire and the actual data collection procedure was carried out during the month of May 2015. 50 subjects were selected by convenient sampling technique. Sample was taken from two classes (Bsc. Nursing 3rd year and GNM interns) of Amar Professional College of Nursing, Mohali, and Punjab.

Results: Results depicted that 72% student nurses had fair knowledge, 26% student nurses had poor knowledge and 2% student nurses had good knowledge regarding Medico – Legal Aspects in care of patients.

Conclusion: Through study, it is concluded that learning opportunity should be given to the nursing students in identifying the importance of Medico-Legal Aspects in care of patients. More emphasis should be given on developing skills and knowledge in the students on Medico-Legal Aspects, so that they can implement their knowledge while caring the patients in clinical settings.

Keywords: Medico-legal aspect, Student nurse

INTRODUCTION

Nurses encompasses autonomous and collaborative care of individual of all ages, family , groups and communities , sick or well and in all settings . Nursing includes the promotion of the health, prevention of illness and the care of ill, disabled and dying people. Advocacy, promotion of a safe environment, research, participation in shaping health policy and in patient and health system management and education are also key nursing roles.

Nursing also includes the use of clinical judgment in the provision of care to enable people to improve, maintain or recover health to cope with health problem and to achieve the best possible quality of life, whatever their disease or disability, until death. Nursing involve the protection, promotion and optimization of health and abilities; prevention of illness and injury; alleviation of suffering through the diagnosis and treatment of human responses; and advocacy in health care for individuals, families, communities and population.

The nurse assists the individual, sick or well, in the performance of those activities contributing to health or its recovery (or to peaceful death) that she would perform unaided if she had the necessary strength or knowledge.

Nursing practice varies both through its various specialties and countries; however, the authority for the practice of nursing is based upon a social contract that delineates professional rights and responsibility as well as mechanism for public accountability. In almost all countries, nursing practice is defined and governed by law, and entrance to the profession is regulated at national and state level.

From all the perspectives of nursing above, it is evident that nursing highly interactive. It then becomes an important necessity for the nurse to be aware of the legal aspects associated with caring and helping people in the health care industry today.

Unfortunately more negligence cases are occurring and less people want to get into the health care field fearing legal aspects and inevitable laws suits.

Employment as a nurse requires a nursing degree as well as the knowledge of the nursing laws that will apply should there be a misunderstanding or challenge by a patient or their family. Many hospitals are not willing to hire nurses without the legal knowledge now that legal issues are becoming more problematic. In order to avoid liability and guard against negligence or malpractice suits. The nurse must be aware of the legal responsibilities of the each aspect of the nursing role. Primary goals of professional accountability in nursing care to maintain high standards of care and to prevent the patients from harm. Nurses should be aware of and be responsible for each action taken, be able to defend their actions and be willing to accept the consequences of their actions personal accountability increases with the degree of autonomy, the higher the degree of autonomy, the greater the accountability, the public trust in a profession increases proportionality to the degree in which the professional members guard and protect the public's interest. Therefore, it is imperative for nurses to be accountable to themselves for proper use of their knowledge and skills in providing care. The Tort law is the aspect to the law that most nurses are more familiar with. This is the law that involves malpractice and negligence cases. Basically a tort is a wrongful act which produces harm, whether it is unintentional or intentional. Malpractice is a specific type of tort where the standards of care are not met. Common ground for Torts is invasion of privacy; assault, battery; false imprisonment; fraud and demotion either as libel or slander. Nurses are affected by law as citizens as employees and as service providers.

As important as the law appears to be in nursing practice, it's very important to assess the knowledge of nurses regarding legal aspects.

OBJECTIVES

To assess the knowledge of student nurses regarding Medico-legal aspects in care of patient.

METHODOLOGY

Research approach: - A Descriptive Approach was used.

Research design: - Non-Experimental Research Design was used.

Setting: - The present study was conducted in Amar Professional College of Nursing, Dyalpura, District Mohali, and Punjab.

50 students were taken as sample including: -

BSc. Nursing 3rd year (20students)

G.N.M interns (30 students)

Sample and sampling technique: - 50 students were selected by convenient sampling technique.

Description of the tool: - Tool was developed after extensive review of literature and experts opinion.

Tool consisted of two sections: -

Section-A: -

Demographic variables: -this section used to collect the information of subjects about their age group, gender, Professional qualification and their previous source of information regarding Medico-legal aspects in nursing.

Section-B: -

Structure knowledge questionnaire: -This section dealt with questions about medico-legal aspects in care of patients consisted of 20 questions

Scoring: - **There** were total 20 questions. One mark was given for each correct response and zero mark for each incorrect question.

RESULT

Result was organized according to objectives

Section A

Distribution of subject characteristics

Table 1:

Percentage and frequency distribution of subjects according to their socio-demographic characteristics.

Socio Demographic Variables	Numbers (F)	% Age
Age		
17-20	6	12%
21-24	42	84%
25-28	2	4%
Gender		
Male	1	2%
Female	49	98%
Professional Qualification		
GNM Interns	30	60%
BSC 3rd Year	20	40%
Previous Source of information		
1. Curriculum		
2. Mass Media	2	4%
3. Others	48	96%

Table 1

Table 1 shows that according to age, 6(12%) subjects fall under age group 17-20 years 42(84%) under age group (21-24 years) only 2 (4%) subjects were from the age group 25-28, according to gender 1 (2%) was male and 49(48%) were female subjects. According to professional qualification, 30(60%) subjects were from GNM Interns and rest 20(40%) were from BSC. Nursing 3rd Year and according to previous source of information, 2(4%) subjects got information from curriculum and 48(96%) subjects from mass media.

Section B

Frequency and Percentage distribution of score according to knowledge.

Table 2

Frequency and percentage distribution of knowledge regarding medico legal aspects in patient care among subjects.

Knowledge level	SCORING	Number (F)	% Age
Poor	0-6	13	26%
Fair	7-13	36	72%
Good	14-20	1	2%

Table 2

Shows that 36(72%) had fair knowledge, 13(26%) had poor knowledge and 1(2%) had good knowledge Hence, it is concluded that most of the student nurses had fair knowledge regarding medico-legal aspect in care of patients.

PIE CHART-Shows that 36(72%) had fair knowledge, 13(26%) had poor knowledge and 1(2%) had good knowledge regarding Medico – Legal Aspects in care of patients

CONCLUSION

It can be concluded from the study that 72% of student nurses had fair knowledge, 26% of student nurses had poor knowledge and 2% of student nurses in Amar Professional College Of Nursing had good knowledge regarding medico-legal aspects in care of patients.

So learning opportunity should be given to the nursing students in identifying the importance of Medico-Legal Aspects in care of patients. More emphasis should be given on developing skills and knowledge in the students on Medico-Legal Aspects, so that they can implement their knowledge while caring the patients in the clinical setting. Nursing students should be made more aware by conducting seminars, conferences and workshops on Medico-Legal Aspects that help to provide quality care by protecting the rights of patients. It can also help nurses to protect their own rights.

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